

New strategies for non-targeted quantification in comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography: The potential of reconstructed TIC response factor surfaces

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Semi-quantification
Response factors
GC × GC
Wastewater

ABSTRACT

Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC × GC) offers unrivaled peak capacity and the ability to resolve and characterize hundreds to thousands of compounds within complex environmental samples. Knowledge of their concentrations is essential in assessing their toxicological and regulatory relevance; however, reliable quantification typically requires concurrent analysis of an authentic standard for each compound. Response factors (RF) may be used to estimate the concentration of a compound without the need for its respective standard, but this is not routinely employed in gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). This study demonstrates that GC × GC offers a new opportunity for the calculation of RFs and estimating a compounds concentration via the creation of 2D total ion current (TIC) response factor surfaces (RFS). A new method, linking a compounds retention time coordinate to its RF using a reconstructed TIC approach, was used to calculate the concentration of 27 compounds in both solvent and effluent wastewater matrix. Using both suspect screening and non-targeted methodologies, average fold change errors of 1.58 and 1.83 respectively were determined for the novel RFS approach. The approach was compared to an RF prediction model utilizing molecular descriptors, using a genetic algorithm, partial least squares regression (GA-PLS) model. The accuracy of the RFS method demonstrates its potential in the fields of suspect screening and non-targeted analysis, where realistic concentration estimates are required. The RFS approach delivers comparable accuracy in concentration prediction compared to computational approaches for determining RFs, but crucially, without the need for generating molecular descriptors or acquiring a reference standard. Additionally, a purely non-targeted approach outlined can allow for the calculation of RF for features without the need for identification or a reference spectrum.

1. Introduction

The thermal conductivity detector (TCD)[1] and flame ionization detector (FID)[2,3] represent two of the first detectors developed and employed in gas chromatography (GC), both during the mid-late 1950s. In the years following the creation and adoption of these two detectors, numerous approaches were developed that allowed for the response factor (RF, the ratio between a compound's detector response and its concentration) of compounds of interest to be determined. This was achieved experimentally[4,5], as well as predicted based on molecular descriptors in the case of FID, using the effective carbon number (ECN) approach, where the RF is proportional to the amount of carbon within the compound [6]. These reference RFs were then used to determine compound concentrations without the need for specific standards,

proving to be a valuable tool for semi-quantitative analysis and offering a distinct advantage in the use of these detectors. For both detectors, lower RFs for more polar compounds were observed, e.g., alcohols and acids, compared to non-polar compounds [4]. The ECN approach has also been applied to the electron ionization mass spectrometer (EI-MS), showing a correlation between the total ion current (TIC) RF and ECN for sets of volatile organic compounds [7–9].

Recently, quantitative structure-property relationship (QSPR) models have allowed for the prediction of RFs in GC; these models rely on mathematically and experimentally derived molecular descriptors to model and predict RF. QSPR approaches were initially applied to data acquired with an FID[10,11] and later to mass spectrometry (MS) detector [12–14]. QSPR models remain a popular means of determining RFs in GC-MS, incorporating molecular descriptors such as molecular

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2025.465811>

Received 24 December 2024; Received in revised form 20 February 2025; Accepted 21 February 2025

Available online 24 February 2025

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weight, logP, polar surface area and fractional ion abundance (most abundant ion in the spectra as a fraction of the total abundance of all ions in the spectra), analogous to the total ion current (TIC) spectra [15, 16]. Use of fractional ion abundance can be more selective than using the TIC response, which may be influenced by baseline signals and coeluting compounds in complex samples, however, the ability to choose a specific, more selective ion would be useful in future strategies. However, when applied to MS, these methods show weaker correlations between experimental and predicted RFs compared to TCD and FID [17]. The more accurate modeling of RFs using TCD and FID is likely resultant from the fact that their response can be largely modelled using a single variable, e.g. the amount of carbon combusted in the FID [18]. Additionally, as with RFs determined using TCD and FID, GC-MS methods tend to yield lower RFs for polar compounds compared to those that are non-polar, with polar surface area, percentage of oxygen atoms and LogP shown to be negatively correlated with response factors [14, 16].

Recently, RF prediction models using mass spectra have been developed for liquid chromatography [19]. Although not yet applied to gas chromatography, this approach is promising for quantification of compounds or features with unknown identities, as it relies primarily on measured mass spectra and retention times [19,20]. This is of interest as comparing and approximating the concentrations of unidentified non-target features may be equally important in prioritising features and characterizing samples [21].

Comprehensive two-dimensional gas chromatography (GC \times GC), developed by Liu and Phillips in 1991, allows for the separation of complex mixtures via two discreet separation mechanisms/columns [22]. Typically, a non-polar column is used in the first dimension, followed by a more polar column in the second [23]. This allows for separation in the first dimension primarily based on boiling-point, while the second dimension separates compounds based on polar interactions. The increased separation power and peak capacity of GC \times GC have made it a powerful tool for targeted, suspect screening, and non-targeted analysis of highly complex samples, such as wastewater [24,25]. The orthogonal separation capabilities of GC \times GC, combined with the tendency of RFs to decrease for more polar compounds in GC-MS (likely due to interactions with active sites in the liner and GC column[26,27] as well as mass discrimination effects[28]) provides a unique opportunity for estimating RF values. We hypothesize that separating compounds in two-dimensional space using GC \times GC can be used to predict TIC RF variability across different compounds. By employing this relationship, it should be possible to estimate a compound's RF based on its position within the 2D separational space, enabling the estimation of analyte concentrations without the need for reference standards. This is particularly relevant for environmental samples such as wastewater, as it enables the assessment of the impact of compounds of interest on both environmental and human health. Furthermore, reference standards of emerging contaminants and transformation products are often unavailable for purchase [29].

In this study, we investigate the dependence of a compound's TIC RF based on its position in the GC \times GC separation space. A 2D response factor surface (RFS) is plotted for a set of 83 training set compounds, where the X, Y, and Z coordinates correspond to the 1D , and 2D retention times and RFs (in terms of TIC) for each compound. This allows the concentration of analytes of interest to be estimated without the need for matching standards.

Approaches are outlined for both suspect screening and non-targeted analysis, depending on the availability of reference spectra. The RFS approach is then validated using an independent set of 27 uncalibrated compounds. The same compound set is also used to develop predictive models using genetic algorithm-based feature selection and partial least squares regression (GA-PLS) models, incorporating molecular descriptors, retention times, and mass spectra. The accuracy and precision of both methods has been validated and compared using the independent validation set of 27 uncalibrated compounds.

2. Methodology

The following methodology section (summarized in Fig. 1) will first detail the TIC Workflow (1.1 – 1.5) used for the generation and application of 2D TIC RFS. The hypothesis and illustration of the reconstructed TIC approach will then be discussed, followed by its application in the Reconstructed TIC Workflow (2.1 – 2.7). This workflow is applied to both Suspect Screening (2.8A) and Non-Targeted (2.8B) approaches.

2.1. TIC approach – workflow 1

To generate a useful 2D TIC RFS, training set analytes with which to build the model should be carefully chosen. These analytes should cover as much of the relevant two-dimensional separation space as possible, as well as the chemical space, in terms of analyte functional groups, boiling points and presence of heteroatoms. Additionally, analytes should not wraparound, meaning their 2D retention times should not exceed the modulation period. To prevent wraparound, an additional run should be executed with a significantly longer modulation period, which in this study was set to 10 s.

1.1 – 1.2, Determination of TIC Response Factor (RF) Values for Calibration Standards. As outlined in workflow 1, Fig. 1, RF for the training set of calibrants detailed in Table S2 of the SI were determined from the slope of their respective linear calibration curves with a fit through the origin, plotting TIC response vs concentration. Following inspection of each calibration curve to ensure linearity and inspect the intercept, a fit through the origin was chosen for simplicity of plotting the slope of each compound as its respective RF. In special cases, such as when there is a co-eluting isotopically labelled internal standard, the TIC response lacks selectivity (e.g., Phenol and Phenol-d6), thus the concentration of the internal standard was added to the respective standard for each calibration level.

1.3, Creation of TIC Response Factor Surface (RFS). TIC RFS were created using the curvefitter app in MATLAB (Version R2023B, MathWorks, MA, USA) using X, Y and Z coordinates corresponding to 1D , 2D retention times and the TIC RF. Within curvefitter, a polynomial surface fit was chosen, with the degree of polynomiality specified in each dimension.

1.4, Determining RF of Compound of Interest. The resultant TIC RFS was then used to determine the RF for the compounds of interest in the validation set detailed in Table S2, using the RFS function determined in MATLAB.

1.5, Using the TIC RFS to Calculate Concentrations of Validation Set Compounds. From this RF, the concentration of the compound of interest was calculated based on its respective TIC response.

Determining Prediction Error of Generated Surface based on Validation Set. The TIC RFS calculated RF for each compound in the validation set was then used to determine the RFS prediction error, relative to the validation set compound's known RF (as shown in Table S2).

2.2. Reconstructed TIC approach – workflow 2

Due to the narrow linear range of ToF-MS detectors, some of the more abundant ions for the respective standards may be overloaded at higher calibration levels, introducing bias into calibration curves based on TIC response. In targeted analysis, this is typically addressed by creating calibration curves using less abundant ions, which ideally remain within the instrument's linear range. Additionally, quantification based on specific target ions offers advantages in terms of selectivity and background noise reduction, especially with high-resolution instruments such as QToF-MS. For example, quantifying a compound using the ion corresponding to its monoisotopic mass can eliminate interference from co-eluting compounds (except isobaric compounds), which would not be discriminated by using the TIC for quantification. To develop and test TIC RFS, but mitigate the issues described above, a reconstructed TIC approach was devised.

Fig. 1. Flowchart illustrating RFS creation using both TIC and reconstructed TIC approaches, as detailed for each process flow in the methodology section below.

Fig. 2 shows the application of this reconstructed TIC approach using a reference MS spectrum of Caffeine (sourced using the NIST mass spectral search program, version 2.4).

Fig. 2(a) shows the NIST reference MS spectrum for Caffeine, whereas Fig. 2(b) shows an overloaded spectrum, simulating an increase in detector response of 40%. As in the reference spectrum 2 (a), in 2 (b) the most abundant ion of 194 m/z also has a normalised intensity of 1000. However, an additional overloaded peak is also observed at 109 m/z in 2 (b), which is of lower intensity in the reference spectrum, 2 (a). This plateauing effect for more abundant ions can therefore result in the TIC response being underestimated for compounds of high concentration, as the true intensity cannot be recorded due to saturation of the three-stage microchannel plate/scintillator/photomultiplier tube detector.

To create a reconstructed TIC from this overloaded spectrum, an ion is chosen which is not overloaded, e.g. m/z 82 as highlighted in green in Fig. 2(b) above. The response of this ion is then multiplied by the ratio of the sum of all ions in the reference spectrum to the ion of interest (referred to here as the reconstruction factor), creating a reconstructed signal, as shown in 2 (c). In order to decrease uncertainties in the reconstructed signal, a number of selective ions should be used for the reconstruction, and the resultant reconstructed TIC signals averaged. Additionally, when possible, “standard”/DFTPP tuning, a tuning option provided with some instruments to keep the relative sensitivity of each m/z channel relatively constant [30], should be used to decrease the variability in absolute sensitivity for each m/z between analytical sequences and improve comparability in the case of using NIST reference

spectra for reconstruction [31].

2.1, Determination of Reconstruction Factor. 2–4 characteristic ions were chosen for the compound of interest. For each ion, a reconstruction factor was then determined, calculated as the ratio of the sum of all ions normalised abundances in a reference spectrum sourced using NIST, relative to the normalised abundance of the chosen characteristic ion.

2.2 – 2.3, Determination of Reconstructed TIC Response. The observed response for each characteristic ion was multiplied by its reconstruction factor, yielding a reconstructed TIC response for each ion. The compound’s reconstructed TIC response was then calculated as the average of these individual reconstructed TIC responses.

2.4 – 2.5, Determination of Reconstructed TIC RF Values for Calibration Standards. RF for the training set of calibrants, detailed in Table S2 within the SI, were determined from the slope of their respective linear calibration curves, which consisted of the reconstructed TIC response versus concentration (as outlined in the previous section). These values were calculated via the target ions and corresponding reconstruction factors (detailed in Table S2) vs concentration, with a fit through the origin.

2.6, Creation of Reconstructed TIC RFS. Reconstructed TIC RFS were generated in MATLAB using the RF values obtained in steps 2.4 - 2.5.

2.7, Determining RF of Compound of Interest. The resulting reconstructed TIC RFS’ function was used to determine the RF for the compounds of interest, in this case, the validation set detailed in Table S2, by applying the “find Z from XY coordinate” in OriginLab.

2.8A, Application for Suspect Screening analysis. The concentration of the compound of interest is determined from its reconstructed TIC

Fig. 2. (a) Reference caffeine MS spectrum; (b) simulating a 40 % overloaded spectrum; (c) reconstructed TIC spectrum, reconstructed as detailed below using characteristic ion (82 m/z) and its respective reconstruction factor.

response (calculated for the validation set using the target ions and corresponding reconstruction factors in Table S2). This approach requires target ions with minimal interference and a reference mass spectrum, limiting its application to suspect screening, where the analyte is anticipated or tentatively identified. Alternatively, a deconvoluted in-house spectrum may also be used as the reference spectrum; this approach is preferred, as in-house spectra will more accurately reflect the relative sensitivity of each mass channel on the mass spectrometer in use, compared to more generic values from reference spectra obtained in other laboratories.

2.8B, Application for non-target analysis. The concentration of a compound of interest is determined from its TIC response. This approach benefits from not requiring the compound's identity or a reference mass spectrum. However, accurate quantification relies on the assumption of spectral purity and the absence of coelution.

Determining Prediction Error of Generated Surfaces based on Approaches 2.8 A/B. RFs for the validation set compounds were determined using the generated RFS. Prediction errors were then calculated based on the known RF, following the formula outlined by Tisler et al. 2023 [32]. calculated as the $FC_{\text{Error}} = RF_{\text{observed}}/RF_{\text{predicted}}$, if $FC < 1$,

$$FC_{\text{Error}} = 1/FC_{\text{Error}}$$

Generation and application of QSPR RF Model using Schrödinger. Compound lists, including chemical identifiers, were uploaded to PubChem to export .sdf chemical structure files. Molecular descriptors were then calculated using Schrödinger Maestro 13.7 (2023–3) with the LigPrep function. The generated structures and descriptors were used to develop a QSPR model using the AutoQSAR function, employing multiple linear regression.

Generation and application of RF Models using PaDEL and the PLS Toolbox. Compound lists, including chemical identifiers, were used to generate molecular descriptors with PaDEL-Descriptor (Pharmaceutical Data Exploration Laboratory, version 2.1). Mass spectra were exported from NIST with each mass channel considered a variable. These variables were then used to create a partial least squares (PLS) regression model in Matlab, using the PLS Toolbox (Eigenvector Research, Inc. version 9.1) after variable selection using a genetic algorithm (GA). The Matlab script and parameters used are provided in the supporting information.

Model Validation. Fold change of the validation set compounds was used to validate the models, calculated as described by Tisler et al. 2023

[32]. calculated as the $FC_{\text{Error}} = RF_{\text{observed}}/RF_{\text{predicted}}$, if $FC < 1$, $FC_{\text{Error}} = 1/FC_{\text{Error}}$

3. Materials and methods

Calibration and Spiked Sample Preparation. Calibration standards and internal standards were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (Schnelldorf, Germany) and prepared in methanol (Honeywell, NC, USA) as described in Table S1 within the SI.

Effluent wastewater, used as the sample matrix, was collected from BIOFOS A/S (Avedøre, Copenhagen, Denmark) on February 8th, 2023, and enriched 500-fold into methanol using a multi-layer solid phase extraction (ml-SPE) method, as described by Tisler et al. [22]. Spiked samples were prepared at five concentration levels (L1-L5, approximately 50, 100, 250, 500, and 1000 ppb) using the compound mix detailed in Table S1.

Sample derivatisation. Each sample was derivatised using N-methyl-N-(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide (MSTFA) under reaction conditions optimised by Lacina et al. [33]. Briefly, 50 μl of sample, spiked with the internal standard mixture, was transferred to a 300 μl GC vial and evaporated to dryness under a gentle flow of N_2 . The residue was reconstituted in 25 μl of Pyridine, and the vial was crimp-sealed. Immediately before sample injection, the autosampler of the instrument added 25 μl of MSTFA into the vial, which was then heated at 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 min to complete the derivatisation reaction.

GC \times GC-QTOF-MS Analysis. Analysis was carried out using an Agilent 7890B GC system coupled to an Agilent 7200 Accurate Mass QTOF mass spectrometer with an EI source (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA). Two-dimensional separation was achieved using a secondary column oven paired with a Zoex ZX2 cryogen-free modulator (Zoex Corporation, Houston, TX, USA). The first dimension separation was carried out using a Rxi-5Sil MS column (60 m, 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μm film thickness), while the second dimension column was a mid-polar Rxi-17Sil MS (1.5 m, 0.18 mm i.d., 0.18 μm film thickness) from Restek (Bellefonte, Pennsylvania, U.S.A). A 0.7 m section of the same Rxi-5Sil MS column as used in the first dimension was used for the modulation loop, and all sections were connected with SilTite μ -union ferrules (SGE Analytical Science, Wetherill Park, Australia).

Samples and standards of 1.0 μl were injected in splitless mode at an inlet temperature of 280 $^\circ\text{C}$. The primary oven was programmed to hold at 105 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min, ramping to 315 $^\circ\text{C}$ at 4.5 $^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, with a final hold of 10 min (total run time of 72 min). The secondary oven and hot jet were maintained at a constant +30 $^\circ\text{C}$ offset from the primary oven, with the column temperature plateauing at 315 $^\circ\text{C}$ and the hot jet at 360 $^\circ\text{C}$. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 2.0 mL/min. The modulation period was set to 6000 ms with a hot jet on-time of 650 ms. Ionization was carried out using an electron ionisation source, operating at 230 $^\circ\text{C}$ with an emission current of 35 μA and electron energy of 70 eV.

Data analysis. Instrument data acquisition was performed using Mass Hunter (Agilent, version: B.07.02.1938), and interpretation of the GC \times GC-MS chromatograms was done with GC Image (GC Image LLC, version: 2.9R1.1). A template was created to define integration volumes for each analyte of interest, including qualifying and quantifying ions. After phase and baseline correction, the template was applied to each chromatogram. The resulting blob tables with relevant TIC and individual ion responses, were exported as .csv for further processing in Microsoft Excel (Version 2105).

4. Results/discussion

4.1. Generation and application of TIC RFS to validation set

As detailed in TIC workflow 1 (Fig. 1), plotting the determined TIC RFs of each compound in solvent as a function of its ^1D and ^2D retention time and using a planar RFS fit (1st degree polynomial in both ^1D and

^2D) resulted in an RFS with a low correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.2435$) and a p value of 0.107 via one-way ANOVA analysis in OriginLab. Since the p-value, exceeds 0.05, the RF fit is not significantly better than using a single RF value for all compounds.

Generation of Reconstructed TIC RFS and Application to Validation Set. As outlined in reconstructed TIC workflow 2, steps 2.1 through 2.7 (Fig. 1), a reconstructed TIC RFS was generated using the training set compounds. The resulting RFS, shown in Fig. 3(a), is described by the function: $f(x,y) = -101.4 + 117.3x + 1417.3y$. This approach, applied to the calibrant compounds, yielded an improved R^2 of 0.3549 compared to the initial TIC method, with a p-value of 0.0306 from a one-way ANOVA, showing a weak correlation between the three variables.

To determine the optimal surface fit, RFS were generated in MATLAB Curve Fitter using polynomial fits of varying degrees, both in ^1D and ^2D , as shown in Table 1., higher R^2 values were observed for higher degree polynomial fits in the ^2D , consistent with the non-linear elution patterns typically seen in ^2D due to the increasing primary oven temperatures. This is supported by both isovolatility curve[34] and retention index surface approaches for ^2D retention indices [30]. A small improvement in the fold-change distribution for the validation set compounds was also observed with higher-degree polynomial fits.

Suspect-screening Approach (Workflow/Methodology 2.8A). Reconstructed TIC responses were determined for the validation set compounds using the procedure outlined in workflow steps 2.1–2.3, with chosen ions and corresponding reconstruction factors detailed in Table S2. The reconstructed TIC RFS (*Re-TIC RFS*) was then used to calculate the prediction error for the validation set compounds, using their respective reconstructed TIC responses. The fold change values ranged from a minimum of 1.01 to a maximum of 2.88, with an average of 1.58, as shown in Table 1. The prediction errors for the validation set compounds are illustrated in the rainfall plots in Fig. 3(b), comparing the RFS approach to RF predictions using average and nearest-neighbour methods. The RFS approach significantly improves the prediction accuracy for the validation set compounds compared to the other methods. The prediction error observed is comparable to the ≤ 2.5 fold error reported by Bergmann et al. 2018, using a predictive model based on molecular descriptors of 147 training set compounds, which was then used to quantify 1550 compounds extracted from silicone wristband passive samplers [14]. The errors are also comparable to the ≤ 2.5 fold prediction error demonstrated by Lum et al. 2022, using a quantitative structure-activity relationship approach, combined with neural networks based on 60 training set compounds [16].

Non-target Approach (Workflow/Methodology 2.8B). Using the non-target approach, the generated surface was used to calculate the prediction error for the validation set compounds using their respective TIC responses, as shown in Fig. 4 (TIC RFS). A broader distribution of fold change was observed with this approach compared to the approach above (*Re-TIC RFS*), with minimum, maximum, and average fold changes of 1.03, 4.54, and 1.83 respectively. Overestimation of concentration is likely in complex matrices due to coeluting compounds. For example, Androsterone TMS (purple point highlighted with a blue circle in Fig. 4), exhibited a fold change of 4.5, occurring in a chromatographically dense region of the GC \times GC chromatogram.

Generation and application of genetic algorithm – partial least squares regression (GA-PLS) RF Model. Modeling of RFs using molecular descriptors was first attempted using the AutoQSAR function within Schrödinger. However, this application operates as a black box, with no visibility of chosen variables, and no user input regarding training/validation set in creating the model.

To have more control over the modelling procedure, PaDEL was used to generate 1444 molecular descriptors for the training and validation set compounds. Following variable selection via genetic-algorithm, a partial least squares (PLS) regression model was created in Matlab, using PLS Toolbox (as detailed in supporting information). Three models were developed using either molecular descriptors (mol), or spectral data

Fig. 3. (a) 2D TIC RFS generated by fitting calibrant ¹D retention times (X-axis), ²D retention times (Y-axis), and RFs (Z-axis) using a planar surface fit in Matlab. (b) Rainfall plot showing prediction error for the validation set compounds ($n = 27$) using the RFS from (a), compared with nearest-neighbour and average RF approaches.

Table 1

Influence of polynomial surface fit degree in the 1st and 2nd dimensions on the fitted surface correlation coefficient (R^2) and corresponding prediction error for the validation set compounds ($n = 27$).

Degree of polynomial fit, 1st and 2nd Dimension	R[2] of RFS Fit	Minimum, Maximum and Average Fold Change Error
1,1	0.3549	1.01, 2.88, 1.58
1,2	0.3656	1.03, 2.66, 1.55
2,1	0.3562	1.02, 2.59, 1.58
2,2	0.3665	1.02, 2.67, 1.55

(spec), or a combination of both (mol + spec); in all three models 1D and 2D retention times were included for the compounds. The resulting R^2 of calibration for the three models was 0.710, 0.869 and 0.784 respectively, as shown in Fig. 5 for the mol+spec model.

Fig. 6 illustrates the prediction error for the validation set

compounds using PaDEL molecular descriptors (mol), mass spectra (spec), and both combined (mol+spec). Whilst the model utilising spectra and retention times only (spec) yielded the highest R^2 of calibration, significant errors were observed in prediction of the validation set compounds, with negative values for several RFs. The model using molecular descriptors, spectral data and retention times (mol + spec) yielded the narrowest distribution of fold change errors, as illustrated in Fig. 6 and Table 2. This model selected 63 molecular descriptors and 59 mass channels after GA, and with the addition of 1D and 2D retention times, resulted in an average fold change error of 1.76 (ranging from 1.01 to 4.76). Interestingly, 2D retention time was a selected variable in all models, reinforcing the utility of the RFS approach, and demonstrating that retention time accounts for some of the variance in the RF for a compound.

A comparison of the prediction errors between the most accurate GA-PLS model (mol+spec) (from Fig. 6) and the *Re*-TIC RFS model (from Fig. 4) for the validation set compounds is shown in Fig. 7 and in Table 2.

Fig. 4. Rainfall plot showing prediction error of validation set compounds using the suspect-screening approach (*Re-TIC RFS*) and the non-targeted approach (*TIC RFS*).

Fig. 5. Measured vs. predicted RF for the model including both molecular descriptors and spectral data (mol+spec), $R^2 = 0.784$.

In addition to a lower average (1.55 vs 1.76) and narrower distribution of fold change errors observed for the RFS approach, we also observe fewer outliers compared to the GA-PLS approach, highlighting the relative accuracy of the method.

RFS for individual compound groups. Both RFS and GA-PLS models were able to predict the concentration of the validation set compounds with reasonable prediction errors, with average fold change errors of 1.55 and 1.76 respectively. However, larger prediction errors were observed for specific compound groups or functionalities. To investigate if the RFS approach could be adapted for specific compound groups, individual RFS were built for individual compound groups. The three models include (1) heterocyclic aromatic compounds ($R^2 = 0.44$), TMS derivatives of alcohols and acids ($R^2=0.37$) and halogenated compounds ($R^2 = 0.37$). Compared to the $R^2=0.34$ for the all-compound RFS model, the observed improvement indicates that compound group specific RFS may improve both the RFS fit and corresponding prediction errors.

Given the dependence of compound group functionality on the quality of the RFS model, specific column combinations may be selected

to optimize the RFS models construction and application for targeted purposes. For example, using a cyano column for the analysis of nitrogen containing compounds, or using a “reverse” orthogonality setup to more thoroughly model the effect of polarity on a compounds response factor.

Effect of Matrix on RFS. In addition to standards in pure solvent, standards were spiked into wastewater extracts to determine the effect of matrix on the creation of RFS and RF prediction accuracy.

Construction of a RFS using standards spiked into a wastewater matrix was shown to improve both the RFS fit, with an R^2 of 0.3722, and the prediction accuracy when compared to the *Re-TIC RFS* constructed in solvent (R^2 of 0.3549), as illustrated in Fig. 8 and summarized in Table 2. The average fold change error for the RFS in matrix was 1.34 (ranging from 1.02 to 2.57). The observed improvement is likely due to consistent matrix effects, where the addition of matrix through injection of the wastewater sample minimises adsorption of analytes to active sites in the system [35].

Fig. 6. Rainfall plots showing fold change error for GA-PLS approaches utilizing molecular descriptors (mol), spectral data (spec), and a combination of both molecular descriptors and spectral data (mol+spec).

Table 2

Summary of R^2 , minimum, maximum and average fold-change errors corresponding to the methods outlined.

Method	R^2 of fit/model	Fold Change Error		
		Minimum	Maximum	Average
Average RF	–	1.01	4.61	1.94
Nearest Neighbour RF	–	1.01	3.76	1.88
TIC RFS	0.244	1.03	4.54	1.83
Re-TIC RFS	0.355	1.02	2.67	1.55
Matrix RFS	0.372	1.02	2.56	1.34
GA-PLS (mol)	0.710	–0.14	8.10	1.83
GA-PLS (spec)	0.869	–10.3	12.86	1.54
GA-PLS (mol+spec)	0.784	1.01	4.76	1.76

4.2. Incorporation of uncertainty into model determined RF

The variation in the calibrant's reconstructed TIC RF (see Table S2 in the SI) is partially dependent on the ion chosen for reconstruction and its corresponding TIC reconstruction factor. In part, this variation was mitigated by using the average of 2–4 ions for calculating the reconstruction factors. However, the reference spectra used to determine these factors were acquired from NIST, which may not directly reflect the spectra acquired on this instrument, as variations in ion intensity readily occur due to instrumental parameters, such as the instrument autotuning. Using an MS with standard spectral tuning capabilities should help minimize these discrepancies, as well as day-to-day fluctuations in ion sensitivity [36]. Creating a RFS that incorporates this, and other sources of uncertainty would further improve the reliability of the reported estimated concentrations. Additionally, uncertainty from the calibration curves used to determine each compound's RF could also be incorporated.

Fig. 7. Rainfall plots illustrating fold change error of Re-TIC RFS and GA-PLS (mol+spec) approaches.

Fig. 8. Rainfall plots illustrating fold change error of RF prediction for RFS built using standards in solvent (RFS) and wastewater (Matrix RFS).

Limitations and future considerations. One potential limitation of this approach is that while the validation set of compounds largely lie within the separational space of the training compounds set (Fig. 9), the entire separation space is not fully covered, and therefore the RFS is not equally well defined across the whole two-dimensional space. Any analytes that are located outside this model range should not be considered for quantification, thus it is very important to select analytes that span the whole usable separational space effectively. However, it should be noted that not all of the theoretical separation space is chemically accessible to analytes in GC \times GC, with fractional coverage typically observed to be below 0.75 [37,38]. Additionally, the linear range of the detector should be considered when predicting the concentration of analytes of diverse concentration, particularly relevant in the case of non-targeted analysis of complex samples.

Perspectives and application of reconstructed TIC approach outside of RFS. In addition to the RFS approach, the reconstructed TIC approach may be useful in targeted analysis where TIC relative response factors are established. In this case, a reconstructed TIC signal used in surrogate should reduce the impact of coeluting peaks and/or detector saturation in both conventional GC-MS and GC \times GC-MS. Additionally, given the use of fractional ion abundance in previous molecular descriptor-based models for determining RF [14], reconstructed TIC spectra and RF may be incorporated into future models.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that reconstructed total ion current response factor surfaces (RFS) in comprehensive two-dimensional gas

Fig. 9. Distribution of training (red) and validation (blue) set compounds within the 2D separation space.

chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC × GC-MS) provide a reliable and innovative method for estimating the concentration of compounds in complex matrices without the need for relevant reference standards. The RFS approach achieved an average fold-change error of 1.55 for suspect-screening and 1.83 for non-targeted analysis, delivering accuracy comparable to or better than predictive modelling techniques, such as genetic algorithm-partial least squares regression (GA-PLS), which yielded an average fold-change error of 1.76. Notably, the matrix-specific RFS further improved accuracy, reducing the average fold-change error to 1.34, highlighting the importance of addressing matrix effects.

By enabling the quantification of both known and unknown compounds, the RFS methodology overcomes critical limitations in environmental analytical chemistry, particularly in scenarios where reference standards for emerging contaminants or transformation products are unavailable. This capability holds significant potential for enhancing regulatory assessments, environmental monitoring, and prioritization of unknown features in non-targeted workflows using GC × GC-MS. Overall, RFS establishes itself as a transformative tool for advancing both suspect and non-targeted screening analyses, offering a versatile and scalable solution for modern analytical challenges.

Supporting Information

Standard and spiked compounds and concentrations, selected ions for reconstruction and corresponding reconstruction factors (PDF).

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jason Devers: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **David I. Pattison:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology. **Asger B. Hansen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology. **Jan H. Christensen:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

This study is a contribution to the VANDALF project, Innovation Fund Denmark, grant agreement no 9067-00032B, in addition to the European Union's Horizon 2020 program D4RUNOFF under grant agreement no 101060638.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.chroma.2025.465811](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2025.465811).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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